

CREATIVE ACTIVITY IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF INDEPENDENT CREATIVE SKILLS OF STUDENTS

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Abstract. *In this article, the formation and development of independent creative activity of students, creative activity is the highest level of independent creative activity. For the formation and development of creative activity, it is necessary to develop creative abilities. Creative abilities are the ability to create something new, understand the need and opportunity, be able to formulate a problem, be able to use the knowledge necessary to put forward a hypothesis, theoretical and practical confirmation or refutation of a hypothesis, search and find other ways to solve a problem, as a result It is the ability to create new original products, scientific discovery, invention, problem solving skills. The article explains his methodology as a solution to this problem.*

Keywords: *competence, creativity, activity, problem, education, process, student, efficiency, research, task, search, hypothesis.*

Introduction. Creative activity is the highest level of independent activity. It is necessary to develop creative ability to form and develop creative activity.

Creativity is the highest form of human activity and independence. Creative abilities are the ability to create something new, to understand the necessity and possibility, to express the problem, to use the knowledge needed to advance the hypothesis, to theoretically and practically confirm or deny the hypothesis, to solve the problem. the ability to search and find other solutions and opportunities, resulting in the creation of new original products, scientific discovery, invention, and problem-solving skills.

The unique feature of the creative process is that it has objective and subjective sides. The objective side is creativity - product innovation, scientific innovation, invention, etc.

The creative process itself is subjective. Therefore, it is necessary to organize the pedagogical process in such a way that what is known to the teacher becomes a discovery for the students. The peculiarity of the development of creative abilities is that they develop during the period of activity, like other abilities. Therefore, this problem is solved. the main task of the teacher in the solution is to search for forms, ways and means of organizing students' creative activity in the process of teaching physics. For example: Research problem. The puck rests on the edge of a horizontal disc. The disk was rotated so that the angular velocity gradually increased. There comes a time when the puck slips out.

The problem in terms of design, how to change a voltmeter to an ohmmeter? Draw a diagram. Do the calculations and assemble the tool.

The nature of the teacher's and students' pedagogical relationship has a great influence on the development of creative abilities during the teaching process. It is recommended to use question-and-answer, discussion and problem method in class, when explaining new material. In such conversations, a teacher-organized dispute-discussion takes place among the students, and different points of view face each other. Creating a conflict requires a lot of work and skill, the result of which justifies the work spent.

Educational conferences and seminars are very useful for the development of creative abilities. In secondary school educational seminars, situations where common interest and controversy arise are the best results of working as a team. For example: Let's take a seminar on the topic of electricity generation, transmission and use. The content of independent study sessions can be approached from the point of view of the development of creative activity of students. In this case, students are not given new knowledge, but at the expense of this, students are encouraged to acquire independent knowledge in new conditions, in the process of interesting work on independent verification, and a system of creative exercises is given. Using creative issues is also an effective method.

The effectiveness of the educational process is determined by the teacher's efforts to activate the independent activity of students. The main task is to educate students' aspiration, inquisitiveness, ingenuity, qualities, organize and form independent educational activities. If a student actively listens to the teacher, performs homework and other tasks in an exemplary manner, studies an independent textbook and other additional literature, participates in science clubs, such an educational process is actively organized. If the teacher explains the topics in an understandable and simple way during the lesson and in extracurricular activities, uses demonstration, as well as technical means of education, new innovative and unconventional methods, taking into account the individual characteristics of students, the educational process is individual and can organize based on the principle of differentiated education, the educational results will be effective. In physics lessons, students can organize their independent creative activities in the following directions: independent study of the text on the subject in the lesson; independent performance of subject-related exercises; solving experimental and computational problems; solving test tasks independently; conducting experiments and observations; work with tables, pictures, graphs, electric circuits; working with visual aids and other educational tools; studying the subject material with the help of a computer; performing physical puzzles, riddles and various individual assignments, tasks, etc.

Regardless of the type, independent work is carried out with the help of certain questions and assignments. Assignments are directed from simple to complex, and each assignment has a specific didactic goal. Separate types of independent work are closely related to each other, and under certain conditions they can be combined.

For example: performing physical experiments can be carried out in a frontal way, in which the activity of students will have a copy character. Experiments are conducted in order to strengthen the learned material. It is known that it is important to increase the cognitive activity of students when organizing independent work in class.

New knowledge is better understood only if students understand the problem and are interested in the work to be done. When setting goals and tasks, it is necessary to take into account the desire of students to learn independently, to express themselves, and to learn. If conditions are created to meet these needs, increasing the interest of students in organizing independent educational activities is a complex issue, and the result of students' effectiveness in the educational process depends on how this issue is resolved.

The teacher considers various aspects of the methodology, taking into account the importance of creating interest in knowledge from the beginning of the lesson. The most important of them are related to 3 situations: firstly, focusing students' attention on the lesson goals and tasks; secondly, to arouse interest in the content of the repeated and newly studied material; thirdly, to

ensure that students enter a form of work that is interesting to them. Active perception of new material occurs in classes where issues related to the problematic tasks of forming students' physical thinking are discussed. In this pedagogical situation, an atmosphere of research is created, in which students begin to solve the problems that are set before them more actively.

Repetition of the learned material can also be the basis for developing and strengthening interest in knowledge and attract attention to the most important issues of the studied material. - theoretical thinking also relies on accepting a firm solution, but it goes beyond its limits and reaches the level of determining generality, which is not given in direct acceptance.

Problem and exercise games, business games, modeling games and other didactic games are used to arouse students' interest in physics. During the game, the activity of each student is shown, a competition appears between some students or teams. Since only students who know the studied material can participate in the game, they see the game not only as a game, but as a serious and interesting activity. The issues of using didactic games in teaching physics are covered to a certain extent in the literature.

Usually, teachers prefer to convey a large amount of information to students, to explain new material mainly by themselves in planned lessons. But practice shows that mastering new material by listening to the teacher's explanation is much less effective than learning it independently under the teacher's guidance. At the same time, there are problematic limits for independent work. If the new matter

Working with textbooks plays an important role in students' independent learning activities. It is very important to regularly work with the textbook in classes to develop the ability to use the method of independent work with the book.

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